

Special Relativity as the Root of Quantum Spin? Part II

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In previous notes, we have argued that a quantum particle, whether it has rest mass or not (photon), carries its own clock and ruler in the form of time and spatial gradations \hbar/E and \hbar/p , where E and p are energy and momentum. A ruler gradation, however, is not enough as the particle exists in three-space and so, as we have argued in a previous note, this sense of three space should also be associated with a physical attribute of the particle for consistency.

In Part I, we argued that spin might follow from special relativity, because for the case of a particle with rest mass, m_0 , it appears mathematically through Dirac's linearization of $EE = pp + m_0^2 c^2$ and for a photon through linearizing: $d/dt \text{ partial } (.5e_0 \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E} + .5/u_0 \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{B}) + \text{grad} \cdot 1/u_0 \mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$ ((1)), where \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} are the electric and magnetic field of a photon. We note, that the Lorentz invariant: $-Et + px$ may be used to suggest that $dt = \hbar/E$ and $dx = \hbar/p$ and so it is not unreasonable, we suggest, that $EE = pp + m_0^2 c^2$ leads to the sense of spin.

As we have argued in a previous note, in order to have an attribute represent the sense of 3-space, one requires an operator. A modulus type equation (such as quadratic equation $EE = pp + m_0^2 c^2$) can hide such an operator, but it may be revealed through linearization. It seems, however, that the presence of such an operator in such a case, must be required. For example, linearizing $EE = pp + m_0^2 c^2$ requires matrix operators and leads to spin 1/2, but for a photon, $m_0 = 0$, and $EE = pp$ is equivalent to $E = pc$ which does not require an operator. Thus, the spin 1/2 picture does not apply to the photon and one must linearize another equation, namely ((1))
In the case of a particle with a rest mass, one may ask: What operator creates $p \cdot p = p_x p_x + p_y p_y + p_z p_z$? In other words, instead of using the three orthonormal vectors (1,0,0), (0,1,0) and (0,0,1) one needs to use matrices. We suggest that matrix multiplication is somewhat similar to a vector dot product (but there are differences) and show that a 2x2 matrix is somewhat like a 4 vector, but that noncommutativity of a matrix leads to somewhat different results. Thus, one may mimic the behaviour of orthonormal vector dot products using matrices, but the feature of a matrix is that it has eigenvalues and eigenvectors suggesting a physical property of a quantum particle, namely its spin.

$\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$ from Special Relativity

In Part I, we noted that $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$ may be obtained by arguing that if a free particle has a kind of $P_1(x)$ and $P_1(t)$, then it must be normalizable which means that there must be a time interval and spatial interval. Traditionally, an arbitrary L is introduced for $P(x)$, i.e $P(x)dx = dx/L$, but we suggested that there should be inherent values and took them from the photon result: $c = E/p$ which holds in all frames. Thus, $dt = \hbar/E$ and $dx = \hbar/p$. This still leaves the notion of 3-space which applies to the p vector undefined by the quantum particle. In other words, one might consider the quantum particle as moving in one dimension with a wavelength \hbar/p and an internal clock with gradations of \hbar/E . The question then arises as to whether a quantum particle may even discern three dimensions in space. To try to answer this, we consider special relativity.

The Lorentz invariant:

$$-Et + px \quad ((2))$$

may be used to obtain \hbar/p and \hbar/E . ((2)) holds for both a photon and particle with rest mass. If one notes that $dx=\hbar/p$ and $dt=\hbar/E$, then the Lorentz invariant does not change.. Thus, this seems like an alternative approach to obtaining $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$, although it seems that the probability normalization one is more direct.

$$\text{Another Lorentz invariant is: } EE = pp + momo \quad (c=1) \quad ((3))$$

This is like a modulus equation. We note that a Lorentz transformation treats E and pc on the same footing with p being the momentum modulus if one uses a 2x2 Lorentz transformation matrix. We argue that there should still be a sense of directions perpendicular to this.

In order to try to see spin arise, i.e. a sense of 3-space, we suggest first that like \hbar/p and \hbar/E , it should be an attribute of the particle. This means that there should be an operator.

Dirac formally linearized ((3)) using $E=i\hbar\partial/\partial t$ and $p = -i\hbar\partial/\partial x$ and found 4x4 matrices.

Here, we will simplify matters by only considering:

$$Pp = p \cdot p = p_x p_x + p_y p_y + p_z p_z \quad ((4))$$

Normally, in linear algebra a dot product brings in the sense of 3-space by using 3 orthonormal vectors:

$$(1,0,0) \quad (0,1,0) \quad (0,0,1) \quad ((5))$$

We note, however, that matrix multiplication is somewhat similar to a vector dot product, although noncommutativity of matrices does lead to differences.

The smallest matrix one may create is a 2x2 one which is like a 4-vector in a sense if one multiplies. Thus, if one has:

$$\begin{array}{l} \begin{bmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} e & f \\ g & h \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{then } (a,b) \text{ multiplies with } (e,g) \text{ and } (c,d) \text{ with } (e,g) \text{ to create two numbers.} \\ \begin{bmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} g & h \\ f & e \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{and } (a,b) \text{ with } (f,h) \text{ and } (c,d) \text{ with } (f,h). \end{array}$$

Given a 2-vector, there are two basis vectors, so one cannot have (a,b) and (c,d) be orthogonal to (e,f) and (g,h) . In other words, one does not get the 0 dot products of the 3- vectors ((5)).

By interchanging the order of matrix multiplication, however, one can change the sign thus creating 0 in such a manner. In other words, 2x2 matrices may anticommute. This is exactly what the Pauli matrices do. Thus, one may create 2x2 Pauli matrices which allow one to write:

$P \cdot p = (p \cdot \sigma)(p \cdot \sigma) = p_x p_x I + p_y p_y I + p_z p_z I$ where I is a 2×2 identity matrix ((6))

The key feature of a matrix, however, is that it may have eigenvalues and eigenvectors as it does in this case. One no longer has a 3 vector, but a 2 vector eigenvector with an eigenvalue which implies a new property of a quantum particle which one may call spin.

This property, however, only occurs if m_0 is nonzero.

The Case of the Photon

In the above description of the Pauli matrices, linearization forces a matrix (as Dirac showed), only if m_0 is nonzero. If $m_0 = 0$ as in the case of a photon, then $E=pc$ and one is not forced to use a matrix. Thus, even though $p \cdot p$ may be written as ((6)), spin $\frac{1}{2}$ does not apply to a photon. A photon, however, should also sense 3-space. In such a case, we suggest looking for a different quadratic equation (still consistent with special relativity) which upon linearization forces a matrix operator to appear.

We suggest that this equation is ((1)):

$$d/dt \text{ partial } (.5e_0 E \cdot E + .5/u_0 B \cdot B) + \text{grad dot } 1/u_0 E \times B \text{ ((1))},$$

In this case, $E \times B = \epsilon_{ijk} E^{(j)} B^{(k)}$, where ϵ_{ijk} is the Levi-Civita symbol.

This symbol may be viewed as a 3×3 matrix with indices j, k and i representing the matrix in question. In this case, one deals with 3×3 matrices directly and so has spin 1. In the m_0 not zero case, one actually has a 4×4 matrix (as shown by Dirac), but it is composed of off diagonal 2×2 Pauli matrices (or the negative of a Pauli matrix). Thus, the 2×2 Pauli matrix is the key for the eigenvalue.

In both cases, a matrix operator appears which is linked to a kind of rotation associated with 3-space. The eigenvalue of these matrices suggests a new quantum property which allows a particle to sense 3-space, we argue.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that a quantum particle has its own built in clock gradation and ruler gradation as physical attributes, \hbar/E and \hbar/p , but should also sense 3-space. For consistency, we argue that this must be due to a physical attribute which should be the eigenvalue of an operator. We suggest that the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ may be used to obtain \hbar/E and \hbar/p and that linearizing $EE = pp + m_0 m_0$ might lead to an operator linked to 3-space. Actually, Dirac suggested this and obtained 4×4 matrices composed of off diagonal Pauli matrices or negative Pauli matrices.

Here we suggest a simpler example by examining $p \cdot p$ as representing 3-space. We note that one usually uses orthonormal 3-vectors $(1,0,0)$, $(0,1,0)$ and $(0,0,1)$. We suggest, however, that matrix multiplication has some similarities to a vector dot product. A 2×2 matrix is then somewhat like a 4 vector, but the interchange of matrix multiplication may lead to an opposite

sign. Thus, for 2-vectors, one only has 2 basis vectors and so will not have a 0 matrix arise from the product of two 2x2 matrices in most cases, if the matrix rows are orthogonal. Thus, one must rely on anticommutation to obtain 0 which is what the Pauli matrices provide.

For the case of a photon, $EE = pp + m^2$, with $m=0$ leads to $E=pc$ which does not force the presence of a matrix. Thus, we suggest one must look for another quadratic equation whose linearization forces the presence of a matrix. In such a case ((1)), the matrix is already present in $E \times B = e_{ijk} E^{(j)} B^{(k)}$ where e_{ijk} is like a 3x3 matrix with indices j,k and a label i . This then leads to spin 1 instead of 2x2 Pauli matrices representing spin $\frac{1}{2}$.